

Data documentation and replication instructions

“Forecasting with Feedback” by Lieli and Nieto-Barthaburu, Economic Journal

We describe the data behind Figure 1 as well as the code used to clean the data and generate the graph. Figure 3 does not rely on any data; the code that was used to generate it is described below.

Raw data files

Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia (2025a):

- **Inflation_realizations_May_2025.xlsx**
This is the raw data on realized inflation (as measured by the GDP deflator), downloaded in May 2025. The data set is in the public domain, and can be downloaded from the Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia:
<https://www.philadelphiafed.org/surveys-and-data/real-time-data-research/p>
On this page use the sublink “All available observations”. The data has quarterly frequency and includes four releases. In the paper we use the last release.
- **Inflation_realizations_May_2025.csv**
This is the same data set in non-proprietary comma-delimited format.

Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia (2025b):

- **GBweb_Row_Format_May_2025.xlsx**
This is the raw data on Greenbook/Tealbook forecasts, downloaded in May 2025. The Federal Reserve of Philadelphia releases these data into the public domain with a 5-year lag. It can be downloaded from:
<https://www.philadelphiafed.org/surveys-and-data/real-time-data-research/philadelphia-data-set>
The first sheet contains detailed documentation of the variables. In particular, the sheet titled gPGDP contains the forecasts for the growth rate of the GDP price deflator over various forecast horizons.
- **GB_gPGDP_May_2025.csv**
This file contains the GDP price deflator forecasts used in the paper in non-proprietary comma-delimited format.

Statement of Rights

We certify that the authors of the manuscript have legitimate access to and permission to use the data used in this manuscript. In particular, all data used in the manuscript are in the public domain as indicated above.

Data cleaning

The main data issue is that there are multiple Greenbooks -- and hence forecasts -- per quarter. We need to assign a single forecast value to each quarter (for any given forecast horizon). There are several sensible approaches: i) select one of the GB forecasts as the representative forecast for the quarter; ii) average the available forecasts. In the paper we follow approach i) but the data cleaning routine presented below includes approach ii) as well to facilitate basic robustness checks.

The outline of the forecast selection algorithm is as follows. The idea is to draw the representative forecast value from a GB that is close to the middle of the quarter. Early in the sample there are usually three GB dates per quarter; we then pick the forecast from the middle one. If the middle GB does not contain a forecast for the given horizon, then we take the next GB; if this GB is also empty then we take the first. If there are two GB dates per quarter (as typical later in the sample) then we pick the first GB; if this is empty, then we take the second GB. The few quarters with four or five Greenbooks are handled similarly (see the code for details).

Another small data issue is that the first and second release of realized inflation have missing data points in one or two quarters. It's natural to resolve this problem by linear interpolation. Note that we use the last inflation release in the paper, which does not have any missing values.

The data cleaning is done by the **Matlab** code:

- **data_cleaning_EJ.m**

This code reads in the raw GB data and assigns a single forecast value to each quarter between 1967q1 and 2019q4 using the chosen approach. The code can deal with multiple forecasts (i.e., forecast horizons or types of forecasts) at the same time. By default, the code is set up to clean the GDP inflation nowcast (gPGDPF0) and the 4-quarter ahead GDP inflation forecast (gPGDPF4) but only the latter is saved in the clean data file. (This is the only forecast used in the paper.) Finally, the code adds the last release of realized inflation between 1967q1 and 2020q4 to the data set.

Required input files: The raw data files `Inflation_realizations_May_2025.xlsx` and `GBweb_Row_Format_May_2025.xlsx`. (Alternatively, one can use the files `Inflation_realizations_May_2025.csv` and `GB_gPGDP_May_2025.csv` if the file extensions are changed in the code.) These files should be placed in the same folder as the m-file (or set up the proper path in the initial "readtable" command).

Output file: The code saves the cleaned data to the csv file "**forecast_data_clean_EJ.csv**". This file will be in the same folder as the m-file.

Running time: negligible on a standard desktop

Matlab release: R2025b

Producing Figure 1

Figure 1 was generated using the Eviews code:

- **rolling_window_mz_EJ.prg**

The code i) reads in the clean data; ii) creates the corresponding Eviews workfile; iii) runs the rolling window regressions needed for Figure 1, and iv) produces both panels of Figure 1 automatically.

Required input file: The clean data file (forecast_data_clean_EJ.csv). **IMPORTANT:** modify the path in the “Load data” section of the prg-file so that it points to the location of the clean data file.

Output file: None. The code produces two graphs which can then be saved or copy-pasted into other applications.

Running time: Less than half a minute in verbose mode on a standard desktop. Faster if the quiet mode is chosen.

Eviews release: Eviews7

Producing Figure 3

Figure 3 was generated using the Matlab code:

- **MZ_slope_sim.m**

The code plots the slope coefficient of the MZ regression function given in part (b) of Corollary 2 in the paper. The code is set up to plot the slope as a function of τ^2 for various fixed values of μ and produces Figure 3 automatically. Another part of the code, which is commented out, plots the slope as a function of μ for various fixed values of τ^2 .

Running time: negligible on a standard desktop

Matlab release: R2025b

Data citations

Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia (2025a). “Data files --- real-time data set (p).” <https://www.philadelphiafed.org/surveys-and-data/real-time-data-research/p> (last accessed: 2026-03-26)

Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia (2025b). “Philadelphia Fed’s Tealbook (formerly Greenbook) data set.” <https://www.philadelphiafed.org/surveys-and-data/real-time-data-research/philadelphia-data-set> (last accessed: 2026-03-26)